

Data Pitch

H2020-ICT-2016-1

Project number: 732506

D7.3 Sustainability strategy and implementation roadmap

Coordinators: Jérémy Decis and Anthoine Dusselier (Dawex)

Quality reviewer: Ryan Goodman (ODI)

Deliverable nature:	Other
Dissemination level: (Confidentiality)	Public
Work package	WP7
Contractual delivery date:	29 June 2018
Actual delivery date:	29 June 2018
Version:	V1.0
Keywords:	Sustainability, roadmap

Table of Contents

Executive summary	3
Introduction	4
Creating a sustainable commercial data innovation ecosystem	5
Creating sustainable data companies	6
Continuing the incubator	7
Conclusion	11

2. Executive Summary

The DNA of Data Pitch is not only to set up an accelerator, to make startups and corporations work together to solve data challenges, but to strongly contribute to the EU-wide data innovation ecosystem. This document explains how Data Pitch will ensure the sustainability of the programme, both in a short term and long term view, while presenting the first outcomes achieved and which can be reused towards this goal.

3. Introduction

The main objective of Data Pitch is to ensure that the innovation space created during the programme and its underlying ecosystem of digital entrepreneurs and investors will continue to thrive after the three years of funding, fostering growth and creativity in the European data market.

Individual partners will take up the experience and results of the project in their own portfolio of services and competencies, building critical mass, strengthening their position and profile as leading European hubs for data-driven innovation, and stimulating further activities and collaborations that complement the Data Pitch efforts.

To make this possible, Data Pitch will build a sustainable European innovation ecosystem in the long term, by:

- defining and addressing key data challenges that are meaningful and relevant to society, industries, and governments;
- reaching out to a critical mass of entrepreneurs with fresh data ideas, who will compete to join the accelerator;
- helping the winners nurture their business in a sustainable way;
- creating new opportunities for the experimenters through networking and introductions to investors and partners.

This deliverable focuses on the different activities Data Pitch will follow to ensure the sustainability of its outputs. These activities include;

- the creation of a sustainable data innovation ecosystem
- the way Data Pitch will enable and support sustainable data companies
- continuing the accelerator

As it addresses important aspects of the exploitation and impact assessment of the Data Pitch programme, this deliverable is closely linked to the D7.1 and D7.2, which cover these topics.

4. Creating a sustainable commercial data innovation ecosystem

The sustainability of Data Pitch rests not only on the success of the accelerator programme, but on its capacity to strongly contribute to the European objectives to build a data driven economy, open and beneficial to every company, whatever its size or level of data expertise.

4.1. Provide companies the data and resources they need

4.1.1. SOTON: allow the experimenters to pursue their work

In the case where data providers wish it, the University of Southampton will continue to host the datasets shared in the lab at least two years after the end of the experiments. This will help startups and SMEs continue their work. Additional resources e.g., the use of Big Data software can be negotiated at preferential rates with the companies past acceleration period.

4.1.2. DAWEX: enable companies to exchange data and unlock its value

DAWEX will provide its Global Data Marketplace to ensure the sustainability of the results of Data Pitch. Our marketplace already provides to 3,800+ companies a secure and trusted way for exchanging data, across borders and sectors. It will allow to give the opportunity to the data providers and startups who have been part of Data Pitch to pursue their activities through Dawex: they will be able to find new relevant data sources, to discover potential partners and innovative companies interested in data, and enable new business models by monetizing their data to other organizations, while retaining full control over the process.

4.1.3. ODI, Beta-i: make resources and materials available after the project

All published materials during the project will continue to exist on the Data Pitch website for 2 years after the project finishes as suggested in Article 28.1 of the grant agreement. We will ensure that the partners continue to share the content created during Data Pitch through their websites and other communication channels, to share to an EU-wide audience the lessons learned from Data Pitch, the success stories and the good practices identified to allow EU companies to fully unlock data's value.

Additionally, content from WP5 on training for open data innovation will be available after the project finishes. The workshops scheduled in WP5 will be recorded and will be available for all the experimenters who has been accelerated.

The workshops delivered during the 2018 accelerator were the following:

- Introduction to the GDPR (presential)
- How to craft contagious content (presential)
- How to run successful marketing campaigns
- B2B sales
- Fundraising 101
- How to raise a seed round

- Getting press
- An introduction to anonymisation assessment (presential)
- How to do twice as much in half the time (presential)
- Defining your purpose and values

4.2. Contributing to EU policies making

4.2.1. Contribute to the “Common EU Data Space” strategy by enabling a transnational cross-sector and cross-organisational innovation space

Based on the assets and impacts generated through the project, Data Pitch will deliver insights around unlocking value of cross-sectoral and cross-organisational data sharing and managing the technical, operational, and legal complexities of a transnational, cross-sector, and cross-organisational innovation space. These insights will focus on the results of the accelerator program from two calls of the project. This work will be carried out in the WP7 by an independent assessor, as explained in the deliverable 7.2 Impact Assessment Framework.

By allowing corporations and startups to work together to solve data challenges, sharing and exploiting data, Data Pitch will generate a number of high-level outcomes about their practices, the kind of data shared, their characteristics, the issues met, etc.

This assessment will focus on:

1. **The inputs, processes, output and outcomes of the competition approach**
2. **Alternative methods of innovation** - referred from reports/research - no additional research required
3. **Impacts achieved on the triple bottom line** (Economical, Environmental, Social)

All of these insights will allow Data Pitch to provide guidance about the best practices for sharing data, the technical and legal requirements as defined by the data providers and experimenters, and the outcomes which can be generated.

Such experience reports are critical to establish a coherent integrated European data market, and could help to support similar future programmes that are funded by the EC, and help the EC to evaluate their decision to fund or not such programmes.

The assessment of the results and the outcomes, the lessons learned from the Data Pitch programme will allow to establish a methodology for representing the impact over time that can be realised from complex innovation programmes, which could be exploited to develop a specific framework used for these purposes.

4.3. Creating sustainable data companies

4.3.1. ODI startup programme and network

Data Pitch’s sustainability strategy is mainly designed around the ODI’s global network framework. Successful startups and SMEs will be invited to become Alumni. The programme provides holistic support to the startups in their development and has successfully graduated three cohorts of data-driven startups since its inception in 2013.

Alongside this support, Data Pitch startups and SMEs will be invited to join the existing ODI network of more than 1,450 businesses, startups, and individuals as Nodes. ODI Nodes are franchises of the ODI and although operate locally, are connected globally across more than 20 different countries.

The ODI model is built to be inclusive. Similar by design to the Web itself, it aims to bring people and organizations together to build an open, collaborative network consisting of so-called 'ODI Nodes'. Each node has to adopt the ODI Charter, which is an open source specification of the ODI itself and its guiding principles. There are three main levels of participation:

- Country: typically, national centres of excellence in any sector, educational institutions, etc.;
- City/regional: organizations running specific projects or activities (training, research, development); and
- Communication: organizations promoting data solutions for the commercial and public good. Participants in Data Pitch (call winners or associate partners) will be given the opportunity to join the network at the city or regional level. A membership at support level with the ODI's own startup programme is already included in our proposition for each sub-grantee as a first step to join the ODI community.

Data Pitch will allow to extend this programme into new countries and markets, in particular by supporting data value chain businesses that use mixed data (open, shared, or closed) to generate impact.

The expanded framework will implement an ecosystem enabling stakeholders to exploit the emerging European data economy along the whole value chain. Bootstrapped by consortium members, this ecosystem is designed to grow further through the existing partner network of the consortium members and an extended network that will be built up throughout the project.

In terms of exploitable assets, the ODI global network, as primary sustainability vehicle, will capitalise on the innovation infrastructure created, including the data (in so far as the data owners are happy to keep it in the lab after the completion of the experiments), and the underlying infrastructure and technology sandbox.

In addition, the Node network will be able to offer bespoke consultancy services around open innovation spanning over a variety of datasets, some more sensitive than others, in many domains and countries. This kind of expertise becomes more and more critical as businesses go global – according to the McKinsey study we quoted earlier in this document, while trade and finance flows are becoming less important, data flows have seen a 45-fold increase in the last decade. Data Pitch will have first-hand expertise on how to establish, technically, legally, and operationally, these critical data flows.

4.4. BETA-I: Open Innovation and Corporate Accelerator Network

Through Beta-i, Data Pitch will also have a credible path to adoption and integration into existing accelerators networks and corporate innovation platforms.

Beta-i is one of the leading European accelerators, delivering over 10 open innovation programs every year, in a wide array of sectors spanning from energy (partnering with 9 global utilities), to smart cities, tourism, fintech, insurtech, pharma, healthtech and others. These programs put in place close to 100 pilots every year, where promising startups work in close collaboration with corporates.

Leveraging that position, Beta-i will keep the Data Pitch alumni involved in that open innovation ecosystem, inviting them to apply to the programs that are applicable to their sector and growth

stage, thus giving those startup alumni a window into a deeper and more sustainable collaboration with corporate entities in their specific sectors.

Additionally, the participation of Beta-i in Data Pitch will provide the company with the knowledge and skills necessary to better deal with the data ecosystem and to push for solutions and startups from that ecosystem in their relationships with corporate entities, as well as in setting up new corporate accelerators or open innovation programs.

4.5. Measure the impacts of data companies

As stated in the deliverable 7.2, Data Pitch will continually assess the experimenters during their acceleration. Both to ensure the success of their projects, and to provide to the market quantified insights of these projects.

What we deem critical for understanding the overall impact of Data Pitch upon the experimenters are the following impacts, which cover the triple bottom line detailed in the D7.2: economic, societal and environmental.

Economic impacts (sometime referred to as value unlocked):

- Sales, the value in Euro of any individual or recurring from selling a data driven product or service
- Investment, any form of venture capital, angel investment, crowdfunding or related funding
- Efficiencies, any quantifiable impact for customers or users for example cost savings.
- ROI of the main projects launched. Experimenters will have to communicate on the potential return on investment/revenue gain that they would have generated through their projects. This KPI should be calculated both in the short and in the long term by each company
- New projects/partnerships signed

Societal and social impacts

- Number of jobs created
- Contribution to the EU social and societal strategy, including
 - Provides greater privacy for individuals
 - Reduces the compliance burden
 - Enables cities to enact smart solutions without surveillance

Environmental impacts

- Contribution to the EU environmental strategy
- Solutions to optimize the management of the energy (Increases energy efficiency and sustainability; and / or combats climate change)

Companies fill in these metrics when they complete the biweekly report which is part of WP5. We also periodically remind them in review meetings and as part of their milestone reviews. The milestone review form includes metrics like revenue, gross profit or monthly active users.

While the tracking during the acceleration happens continuously, surveying metrics like investments happen on a more ad-hoc basis after the graduation. Touch points are significant

news, events, and as part of other feedback mechanisms. Some sales cycles, and even more so investment funnels, are often longer than a few months. A critical meeting with a mentor during the incubation period may only convert into a sale after a number of months and therefore it is important to collect these metrics beyond the acceleration period.

The ODI will continue to measure and collect the impact of companies after the Data Pitch project finishes. The metrics are published, for example, as aggregate statistics in the ODI's dashboards 4 and in many other communications that relate to the Open Data Incubator (See Deliverable 7.2 [Impact Assessment Framework]).

5. Continuing the incubator

5.1. Key figures of the first call

The call received 142 applications from 23 countries within the H2020 network (see Figure 1 below). The full details of these are recorded in the deliverable 4.2.

Figure 1 Map of Data Pitch call - round 1 applicants

The map below shows the geographical spread of applicants. Data pitch received applications from 23 countries within the H2020 network.

Over 57% of applications were made to sectoral challenges, over 23% to data provider challenges and 20% to open innovation ones. The five challenges that received the most applications were as follows:

1. Health & wellness (20.4%)
2. Open innovation (19.7%)
3. Smart manufacturing (11.3%)
4. Tourism (10.5%)
5. Empowering users online (9.9%)

More details are provided in Figures 2 and 3 below.

Figure 2 Number of applications per challenge

The chart below provides a more detailed breakdown of the number of applications per challenge, and those who made it through to the interview stage.

Figure 3 Number of applications interviewed per challenge

The chart below provides a more detailed breakdown of the number of applications per challenge, and those who made it through to the interview stage.

5.2. Second call expectations

For the second call, thanks to the lessons learned in the first round, we expect to double the number of data providers, and to increase the number of applicants to the call.

This will allow Data Pitch to prove and analyse new ways of extracting value from data, thanks to a higher number of challenges to solve from various business sectors, and new cooperations between data providers and startups & SMEs.

5.3. Create a service model

The Data Pitch accelerator is a product that can be utilised to accelerate startup and SME’s working with shared data. This programme provides up to 50 startups support, advisorship and mentorship over a 6 month period to help scalability.

The success and use of the acceleration programme will be due to the quality and relevancy of all services provided. In order to enable all the services to be fully utilised and recognised, consortium partners will ensure their open accessibility. The programme also features control mechanisms such as milestone reviews and bi-weekly reports to track the performance and track engagement with the services.

The accelerator has been designed to become self-sustaining after the end of funding, thanks to a series of high-value assets:

- The innovation sandbox used by the experimenters during their acceleration, alongside the open innovation and legal framework created, have the potential to be re-used for similar purposes;
- The in-depth knowledge about how startups and SMEs become successful in the long-term in the global data market. As open innovation remains a strategic priority for any type of

organisation, these assets will be of interest for virtually any digital business or government. This will help in securing new opportunities and expanding on our portfolio.

We will leverage the lessons learned in experimentation and acceleration to create a service model that maps well to the business of the ODI and BETA-I.

Data Pitch will collect and promote proven-and-tested business models and success stories, distilled from the experiences gained by running the competitive call, engaging with experts, investors and the general public, and mentoring early-stage companies in developing ideas and growing their business. It will also offer advice to policy makers in the area of data privacy and ensure that the ecosystem built through Data Pitch will mature.

6. Conclusion

The Data Pitch sustainability strategy is built on a combination of different approaches, and is not limited to the activities performed during the 36 months of H2020 funding.

All of these approaches, combined, ensure to Data Pitch the capability to build a sustainable innovation ecosystem reaching beyond the end of the three years of public funding.

The aims of Data Pitch partner are well aligned with the aims of the Consortium, ensuring

- The mission of the ODI is to “connect, equip and inspire people around the world to innovate with data”; they run a thriving international network of like-minded Nodes and have successfully run national and international startup programs.
- Beta-i has helped hundreds of startups and entrepreneurs through promotion, networking, and acceleration; they are the driver of Lisbon Challenge, one of the most ambitious, international, and successful accelerators in Europe.
- DAWEX has a main claim and ambition to make data the fuel of the growth, by facilitating its movement between organisations, allowing companies, whatever their size and business sectors to share and exchange data
- University of Southampton, Institute for Law and the Web (ILAWS): ILAWS is a research centre that focuses on the examination of “legal issues, problems and opportunities associated with the Internet, the web and digital technology”; in particular key areas of IT and IP law. ILAWS works closely with colleagues from other disciplines, e.g. cyber security, psychology and web science. (For further information visit our webpages at <<https://www.southampton.ac.uk/ilaws/about/index.page>>)
- University of Southampton IT Innovation: IT innovation is funder member of the BDVA association and it is actively involved in the activities at European level aiming at promoting the exploitation of data. IT Innovation is also involved in industrial relationship where we are bringing the experience and competence gained within Data Pitch as the technology transfer to the industry is one of the goals constantly pursued by the Centre.
- University of Southampton Web and Internet Science: Soton WAIS has been, and continues to be involved in multiple data-driven innovation projects across a variety of sectors including smart cities, crowd-sourcing and open, closed and shared data. WAIS has already successfully replicated the model developed in Data Pitch for the Interreg 2Seas project Smart Cities Innovation Framework Implementation.

Exploited together, these assets provide Data Pitch the capacity to enable a complete and yet unique data innovation ecosystem aligned with the ambition of the European Commission, which is to create and support a data driven economy.